

VISIBLE LEARNING - TEACHING STRATEGIES FOR ROMANIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE

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Abstract

The benefits of visible learning in teaching Romanian are multiple: students become more responsible for their own learning, which leads to increased performance, whether it is creative writing, literary analysis or oral expression. Students who are aware of their progress and assessment criteria are less stressed and better prepared for tests and exams, visibly reducing testing anxiety. When students understand the purpose of the activities and see the results of their work, they are more motivated to learn. We propose the ILIADA method, which does not replace existing methods but complements them through integrated activities aimed at developing students' competencies. This approach involves solving real-

world problems in diverse learning environments and producing concrete academic outcomes. By integration, we mean coordinating and combining various elements into a functional whole.

Keywords: visible learning, ILIADA, teacher, student, tools, performance, digitalization.

The Importance of Visible Learning in Teaching Romanian Language

Visible learning was addressed in John Hattie's rigorously documented work, *Visible Learning: A Guide for Teachers*, a reading on learning effectiveness, a contribution to the teaching-learning-assessment process aimed at all those involved and interested in the field of education. This work is based on research conducted over the last decades. The guide presents lesson sequences and emphasizes the educational relationships created between the main actors in the field: teachers, students, and school principals. The book is full of practical advice for selecting the best teaching strategies and is complemented by exercises suitable for different stages of the teaching process.

What is visible learning? John Hattie mentions that "the visible aspect refers to making students' learning visible to teachers, ensuring clear identification of the attributes that make progress in students' learning visible, but it also refers to the fact that everyone in the school should visibly know the impact they have on learning". Learning is visible not only to the teacher but also to the student. Through this approach, the student becomes their own teacher, capable of improving their self-education process. Therefore, teaching must be considered from the perspective of the impact it has on the student.

Thus, we speak of visible learning when, in a space that offers safety and trust, the objective is clearly stated and both teacher and student are motivated to achieve it. Speaking of motivated teachers, John Hattie specifies that they „do not

use grading as a punishment, do not mix academic and behavioral performance, do not promote quiet compliance over schoolwork, do not overuse worksheets, do not have low expectations and are not advocates of ‘he can only do so much,’ and do not prefer perfect homework over taking risks that involve mistakes”.

The student is seen as a partner in the teaching-learning process, treated fairly and respectfully, with independence and autonomy encouraged in the classroom. It is very important to remember this, as in daily work, focused on tasks and objectives, teachers tend to dominate the entire process, forgetting that results depend on the work of the whole team. In this case, the teacher must have the ability to step back when they notice that the student is progressing toward the proposed objective. The teacher then assumes a supportive role, assuring the student that they are on the right path in completing the task.

When we talk about progress and performance, we often associate them with elite schools. It is uninspired to believe that only in these schools quality education occurs, that only there are the best teachers, and that only there learning is visible to teachers, students, and the community. Learning becomes visible wherever the teacher wants to evaluate the impact their work has on students, regardless of the school they are in. This is also the message Hattie addresses to all teachers: „My role as a teacher is to evaluate the impact I have on students”.

Regarding visible learning, we notice that it often becomes visible at the end of a learning cycle or after national exams. However, it is important that this practice becomes frequent, even permanent, so that progress can be recorded or remediated where necessary. If our goal is to work in a school where learning is visible, we must identify ways for it to be easily recognized.

Visible learning is a pedagogical approach focused on clarifying learning objectives, monitoring progress, and providing constant feedback. It requires that teachers and students have a clear understanding of what is being learned, why it

is important, and how progress can be evaluated. In the context of teaching Romanian, this method is essential for developing linguistic, literary, and communication skills.

The key aspects of visible learning in teaching Romanian involve clear learning objectives, progress monitoring, constant feedback, the use of visual and practical tools, and student involvement in the learning process. In teaching Romanian, it is crucial for students to understand the purpose of the activities: for example, learning a grammatical rule, developing vocabulary, or understanding a literary text. Setting clear objectives helps students know what is expected of them and become more aware of their own learning process.

The benefits of visible learning in teaching Romanian are multiple: students become more responsible for their own learning, leading to increased performance, whether in creative writing, literary analysis, or oral expression. Visible learning encourages students to analyze, synthesize, and evaluate information, skills essential in studying Romanian. Students who are aware of their progress and assessment criteria are less stressed and better prepared for tests and exams, visibly reducing test anxiety. When students understand the purpose of activities and see the results of their work, they are more motivated to learn.

Principles of Visible Learning Applied to Romanian Language Teaching

Visible learning is considered a priority for Romanian education in the 21st century, as it can substantially contribute to improving the quality of education by motivating students and developing the skills and competencies necessary in a constantly changing world. In recent years, Romanian education has undergone major reforms aimed at improving the quality of education. Visible

learning is the solution for implementing these reforms by actively involving the main participants in the educational process: teachers and students.

The principles of visible learning emphasize clarity, monitoring, and engagement, transforming education into an active, personalized, and efficient process. By applying these principles, teachers can provide students with the tools necessary to become autonomous, motivated, and well-prepared for future challenges. Visible learning relies on clear objectives, progress monitoring, and the use of feedback to improve student performance. Applying these principles in teaching Romanian can transform the educational process, making it more interactive and effective.

Visible learning places a strong emphasis on assessment methods and feedback, so that students can clearly, consistently, and continuously see where they are and what they need to do to improve their performance. This can be achieved only if teachers set precise objectives, organize formative assessments, and use peer assessment and self-assessment techniques. (Piaget, 2005. p.97)

Another important component of visible learning is collaboration. Students, encouraged to work together - in pairs, teams, heterogeneous or homogeneous group - and to share their ideas and perspectives, can more easily learn from one another and develop communication and collaboration skills. The primary goal of visible learning is not merely knowledge acquisition but competency development. This requires the cultivation of critical, creative, and reflective thinking skills, as well as problem-solving and decision-making abilities. To implement visible learning in the instructional process, a radical change in the educational approach is necessary: the focus should be on the learning process rather than solely on final outcomes. Teachers must always be prepared to provide constructive feedback and remain open to change and innovation.

Visible education involves the use of tools and strategies that allow both students and teachers to better track and understand the learning process, including the use of technology, progress monitoring tools, or online platforms for collaboration and feedback. It can also be realized through active learning methods such as group discussions, role-playing, and practical projects.

With the implementation of visible learning, students can monitor their own progress and self-assess their performance, which can help increase self-confidence and develop the ability to manage their own learning process. Teachers can use visible learning to improve their teaching practice by monitoring student progress and providing constructive feedback in real time, which can help identify weaknesses in the learning process and develop strategies to enhance performance. (Cerghit, 2006. p.98)

Based on the premise that visible learning—a concept developed primarily from the research of John Hattie—emphasizes a clear understanding of how students learn and the use of methods that maximize teaching effectiveness, and requires that learning objectives, progress, and outcomes be „visible” to both students and teachers, we can rely on ten principles of visible learning applied to teaching the Romanian language.

ILIADA method – theoretical foundation, implementation and methodological delimitations

The ILIADA method is an integrated instructional model grounded in interdisciplinary and competency-based education. It is designed as a project-based learning framework that complements traditional instructional approaches by shifting the focus from content transmission to active knowledge construction.

The theoretical foundation of the method combines constructivist learning theory, experiential learning, and the principles of visible learning, emphasizing

that learning becomes more effective when students actively construct meaning through engagement, reflection, and feedback (Piaget, 2005; Hattie, 2014).

From a methodological perspective, ILIADA operates as an applied instructional design model implemented through structured interdisciplinary projects. These projects typically extend over 2–4 weeks and require students to engage in collaborative inquiry, problem-solving, and production of authentic learning outcomes such as digital portfolios, creative texts, artistic artifacts, or multimedia presentations.

The implementation of the method is based on a progressive learning cycle:

- First, a meaningful interdisciplinary theme is selected in relation to curricular objectives and students' lived experiences. This ensures relevance and cognitive engagement.
- Second, learning outcomes are defined in terms of competencies rather than isolated knowledge, aligning with modern curriculum standards.
- Third, students are organized into heterogeneous groups to encourage collaborative learning, peer interaction, and role distribution.
- Fourth, tasks are distributed across disciplinary domains, allowing students to approach the same theme from multiple cognitive perspectives (historical, literary, artistic, technological, and digital).
- Fifth, students engage in iterative production processes, where feedback is continuously integrated to improve outcomes.
- Finally, learning is consolidated through public presentation and structured reflection, which makes learning outcomes visible and assessable.

Research status: At its current stage, the ILIADA method represents a theoretical-applied educational model. Its effectiveness is intended to be validated through action research methodologies, involving systematic

observation, formative assessment, and comparative analysis of student competencies before and after implementation.

Limitations of Implementing the ILIADA Method

Although the ILIADA method introduces an innovative and flexible framework for interdisciplinary learning, its implementation presents several pedagogical and organizational constraints that must be considered.

One significant limitation is the increased demand for instructional planning time. Because the method relies on interdisciplinary coordination, teachers must design integrated tasks, align learning objectives across subjects, and manage complex classroom dynamics. This may be challenging in contexts where curricula are already densely structured.

Another limitation concerns teacher readiness. Effective implementation requires pedagogical competence in interdisciplinary teaching, collaborative learning facilitation, and the use of digital tools for learning production and assessment. Without adequate professional training, the methodological potential of ILIADA may not be fully realized.

Additionally, assessment practices within interdisciplinary projects may present difficulties, particularly in ensuring consistency and transparency of evaluation criteria across different domains. This necessitates the development of clear rubrics and formative assessment frameworks aligned with competency-based education.

Despite these constraints, the method retains a high degree of adaptability. Its structure allows contextual modification according to institutional resources, student profiles, and technological availability.

Assessment of Progress within the ILIADA Method

Assessment in the ILIADA framework is conceptualized as a continuous, formative, and competency-oriented process rather than a final measurement of knowledge acquisition.

This approach is grounded in the principle of visible learning, where both teachers and students are able to monitor learning progress in real time and adjust strategies accordingly (Hattie, 2014).

Assessment is operationalized through **multiple complementary instruments**:

- Systematic observation allows teachers to monitor collaboration dynamics, participation levels, and problem-solving strategies during project activities.
- Portfolios (individual and group-based) provide longitudinal evidence of learning development, capturing both process and final outcomes.
- Self-assessment and peer assessment promote metacognitive awareness, enabling students to critically reflect on their own learning progress and that of their peers.
- Formative feedback, delivered continuously throughout the learning cycle, functions as a regulatory mechanism that supports improvement rather than judgment.
- Assessment criteria are explicitly aligned with competency development, including engagement in learning tasks, quality and originality of produced outputs, collaboration skills, digital literacy, and individual learning progress relative to defined objectives.

The effectiveness of the method is best examined through an action research design, which allows iterative refinement based on classroom evidence and continuous pedagogical adjustment.

Example of a Project:

Theme: FRIENDSHIP

Dilemma: “You have the chance to travel back in time and listen to a secret conversation between Mihai Eminescu and Ion Creangă. How would this experience influence our imagination and creativity?”

Title: The Secret File of the Great Classics

- School Products: research magazines, educational infographics, video projects, digital portfolios, multimedia presentations, models, posters, essays, applications, or websites.

Domain: HISTORY: Students research the lives of Eminescu and Creangă, investigate contemporary publications, analyze memoirs and letters, describe 19th-century lifestyles, reconstruct the atmosphere, and synthesize collected data to corroborate and transcribe it into a manuscript.

Domain: ROMANIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE: Students write messages and leaflets, prepare speeches, start a debate club, imagine conversations between writers, create infographics and posters, compose dramatic texts, and perform them in roles.

Domain: ENGINEERING: Students set up a TV studio, install microphones and lighting, design and sew period costumes, and create models and exhibitions.

Domain: ART: Students draw, paint, photograph, decorate the stage, improvise performances, and design graphics for models.

Domain: DIGITALIZATION: Students program and edit, create digital collages, digital books, videos, and photo albums.

Domain: ACTION: Students publicly present their outputs, organize interactive exhibitions and cultural weeks, distribute leaflets, and promote project activities.

Examples of Dilemmas for the Project

- Identity and Cultural Heritage: How does knowing the lives and works of writers influence students' cultural identity?
- Technology and Social Change: How did 19th-century technologies change daily life?
- Evolving Values and Traditions: How have societal values evolved, and what role did major historical events play?
- Adapting to Change: How did people manage social and material changes in the past?
- Innovation and Creativity: What were the literary and technical innovations, and how did they influence culture?
- Memory and Remembrance: How do contemporaries preserve classical works, and how can they be passed to future generations?
- Knowledge and Lifelong Learning: What lessons about language and literature can we learn from the lives of great writers?

Examples of Tasks for Each Domain

HISTORY

- Conduct an imaginary interview with the two writers, using historical documents and testimonies.

- Create a visual timeline of significant historical events in the writers' lives.
- Write an essay on the impact of historical events on Eminescu and Creangă.
- Prepare a PowerPoint presentation on an important 19th-century historical event.

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- Write a short fictional story about a day in the writers' childhood.
- Compose a poem inspired by the writers' lives and testimonies.
- Write an argumentative essay on friendship using examples from their biographies.
- Create imaginary interviews with Eminescu and Creangă.

ENGINEERING

- Build a model of a technology used in the writers' childhood.
- Design and construct a model of the Humulești house.
- Create a simple device illustrating a technological innovation from that period.

ART

- Create collages of photos and artistic elements inspired by the writers' era.
- Paint or draw illustrations representing stories and memories.
- Organize a school art exhibition.
- Produce a short documentary film about the writers' lives.

DIGITALIZATION

- Create a digital album with photos and documents.
- Make digital presentations comparing modern technologies with 19th-century ones.

- Design a mobile app for collecting and organizing literary texts.

ACTION

- Organize a project launch day and present creations.
- Perform role-playing and dramatizations of literary fragments.
- Hold a cultural event and awareness campaign in the community.
- Role of the Student in the Project

The student presents, discusses, demonstrates, explains, argues, interprets, organizes, coordinates, creates, promotes, participates, collaborates, develops, publishes, and communicates. In this way, the literary text becomes a desire for knowledge, and the student becomes an active participant in their own education, developing self-esteem and interest in cultural values.

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